

The Extent Of Engagement To Social Networking Sites, The Impact Of Playing Mobile Games, And The Students' Learning Experiences: An Assessment

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Abstract: This study aimed at evaluating the extent of the engagement to social networking sites, the impact of playing mobile games and the degree of learning experiences among the first year Bachelor of Science in Information Technology (BSIT) students in a State University in Central Luzon, Philippines to provide a basis for designing intervention programs and improving the existing programs and activities of the college. It utilized a mixed method of research, employing a descriptive design to describe the evaluation made by the Information Technology (IT) students as the respondents of this study. A total number of 500 first year students participated in this study during the Academic Year 2019-2020 by answering a self-made survey questionnaire which passed the content and reliability analysis made by the researchers. Results show that there is a large extent of engagement to social networking sites among IT students. The positive and negative impacts of playing mobile games were identified and evaluated, and the degree of learning experiences show that IT students frequently and actively engaged, participated, attended, and involved in different activities essential for their holistic development. The results of this study contributes to the body of knowledge focusing on evaluating the extent of engagement to social networking sites, mobile games, and learning experiences and may provide new opportunities and insights for future researches.

Index Terms: Degree of Learning Experiences, Engagement to Social Networking Sites, Evaluation, Impact of Mobile Games, Information Technology, Program Intervention

1 INTRODUCTION

The advent of technological advancements and innovations over the past decades has greatly affected the lives of every individual. Today's generation has witnessed the radical changes brought by these advancements, and Information Technology (IT) was one of the key driving forces of these changes. Information Technology is "the study of systematic approaches to select, develop, apply, integrate, and administer secure computing technologies to enable users to accomplish their personal, organizational, and societal goals" [1]. The fourth industrial revolution or Industry 4.0 is fueled by the emergence of IT solutions – from simple automation of daily tasks and activities to complex organizational procedures - IT solutions have been embedded to support different processes. Today, different driving forces through IT innovations that contributed in shaping the world continuously increased. These include Mobile Applications, User Experience, Internet-of-Things (IoT), Big Data, Cyber security, Automation, and Social Platforms [1]. Social Platforms include social collaborations, social feedback, and social media. These progresses have huge impact on how people live their day-to-day lives.

Several advantages and disadvantages can be identified since many people have already been using different social media platforms and social networking sites every day. Social media is a means to facilitate social interactions among different individuals through a connected network. It enables people to collaborate and to reach larger group around the world. More specifically, social media is comprised of different Online Social Network Sites (OSNs). OSNs are Internet-based locations that allow individuals to network with one another. Interactions in OSNs include meeting other persons by exchanging information, or communicating through chat or video calls. An OSN lets people to create public or semi-public personal pages that contain personal information based on their own choosing. OSNs include Facebook, Twitter and Youtube [2]. SimpliLearn [3] asserts that people typically involve themselves in different OSNs because they would like to raise or support a cause or issue they feel strongly about, to share valuable information and influence others, build image and demonstrate who they are and what they stand for, and participate and feel involved in different things happening around the world. These common reasons are the typical reasons why the younger generations utilize social networking sites most of the time. Since social networking sites have provided a means to communicate with different people around the world, the way how people communicate and interact have changed and evolved over time. OSNs have greatly affected different areas including politics, society, and commerce, world of work, and training and development [4], [5] and [6]. Researchers have published studies claiming that social media including different social networking sites have greatly affected the interpersonal relationships, mental health and well-being of individuals, thus it can be understood that social media have distinct impact in the holistic development of a person. The challenge of the 21st century teaching and learning in different educational institutions was to help students acquire and develop the necessary skills needed to fully realize one's full potential. Skills which include critical thinking, collaboration, communication, creativity, and the

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ability to connect to the world are the essential 21st century skills expected from students today. The internet have greatly affected the way how students realized and developed their potentials. Advantages and disadvantages were evident hence it was necessary for educational institutions to strengthen the programs being offered to the students in order to aid them and further improved their academic performances. Through OSNs, family relations can be strengthened, thus performance can be improved because students' satisfaction with their family and friends is shown as supported by the use of social networking sites. This is supported by [7] citing that social media make students enjoy meeting new friends, communicating with others online, and establishing collaboration among students. Muaña [8] supports the idea that social media and OSNs are used for communication purposes, and adds that it is also used to gather or look for new information and for entertainment purposes such as online games. However, [7] explains that social media does not support the learning of the students. Furthermore, excessive use of social media among students became negative due to the time spent on the communication medium [9]. In the university, social media platforms and different social networking sites have contributed to the overall college learning experience of the students. The Education Reform [10] defines learning experience as any interaction or experience in which learning takes place. This may happen inside or outside the academic setting. Inside the academic setting includes the school and the classroom environment, while outside the academic setting includes the outside-of-school locations or outdoor environments in which learning takes place. Learning experience also includes traditional education interactions or nontraditional interactions. IBE [11] explains that learning experience should be challenging, interesting, rich, engaging, meaningful, and appropriate to the needs of the learners. In a nutshell, learning experience refers to the overall experience of the students to acquire new knowledge, skills, and values. Chalapati, Leung and Chalapati [12] cites the common factors affecting the learning experience of college students which include interactive teaching techniques, peer support, program attributes, social integration, and the international learning environment. College learning experience may be caused by several other factors that can lead to students' satisfaction in higher education learning institutions. Students' satisfaction in the college learning experience includes personality grooming, personal values, and psychological needs fulfillment [13]. College learning experiences may be attributed from various sources – curricular, non-curricular, and co-curricular activities. Today, engagement to mobile games is one of activities by college students which may be considered as one of the sources of learning experience, if utilized properly, positive impacts can be achieved. This has been supported by [14] stating that playing mobile games have no significant negative impact on the academic performance of the students. Rather, playing mobile and online games boost the social behavior of the respondents. This can be considered as an indicator that mobile and online games have more positive impacts in the academic performance of students. Ali [15] asserts the other positive and negative effects of mobile and online games. They found out that engagement to online games enhances the cognitive functions, improves decision-making skills, develops hand and eye functions, and enhances teamwork. However, negative effects are comprised of aggressive

behavior, causing an individual to become a loner, develop wrong set of values, acquire negative impact on health, and may cause bad academic performance. The extent of engagement to social networking sites, the impact of playing mobile games, and the degree of learning experiences were the variables involved in this study. The researchers assert that there was a need to conduct this type of study to fill-in the gaps in terms of knowledge and practice. Knowledge gap was one of the gap the researchers wanted to fill-in as far as the study about evaluating the extent of engagement to social networking sites, the impact of playing mobile games, and the degree of learning experiences was concerned. There was also a need to contribute to the body of knowledge to shed some light regarding to the topic on hand. Also, the gap related to providing a basis for developing intervention programs and/or enhancements was also another gap that the researchers wanted to fill-in. This study aims to evaluate the extent of engagement to social networking sites, the impact of playing mobile games, and the degree of students' learning experiences to provide a basis for future intervention programs and activities.

Specifically, this study was aimed at:

1. Determining the extent of engagement of the BSIT students to social networking sites.
2. Describing the impact of playing mobile games to the BSIT students?
3. Describing the degree of learning experiences among BSIT students?
4. To provide a basis for developing program intervention to improve the learning experience of the IT students.

2 METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a mixed method of research design. Mixed method is a developing research method design that utilizes both quantitative and qualitative approaches. The researchers used mixed method to perform triangulation. Triangulation provides an opportunity to merge and verify the results of different research methods to fully understand the phenomenon under investigation [16]. This study applied methodological triangulation because observations, questionnaires and interviews were conducted to gather and confirm the results [17]. Furthermore, triangulation was done to enrich, refute, confirm, and explain the findings of this study. Through triangulation, the researchers were able to draw insights which can contribute to the existing body of knowledge [18].

2.1 Research Respondents

In administering the survey questionnaires, the researchers explained the content of the survey and allowed the respondents to read and analyze the contents before answering. During the first semester of AY 2019-2020, the researchers conducted a preliminary observation on the engagement of IT students to mobile games. Based from the observation, the most common mobile games played include mobile legends, clash of clans, etc. Students were observed to be very interested and fond in these mobile games. Also, the researchers conducted an initial interview on the students learning experience. Results of observation were used to refine the self-made questionnaire. In the start of the second semester of AY 2019-2020, the instruments were handed-out

to the respondents and the evaluation happened.

2.2 Research Instruments

Three sets of questionnaires were distributed composed of The Extent of Engagement to Social Networking Sites Questionnaire, The Impact of Playing Mobile Games Questionnaire, and the Student Learning Activities Questionnaire. The three questionnaires were self-made based from reviewed studies, articles, and literatures to suit the needs of this undertaking. The questionnaires have undergone content validity and reliability to ensure the effectiveness of the instrument being used. Content validity was done by allowing some experts and researchers in the field to review the content, while the reliability analysis was based from the result of the reliability testing conducted by the researchers. Table 1 presents the results of the reliability analysis.

Table 1. Reliability Analysis

Instrument	Cronbach Alpha	Number of Items
The Extent of Engagement to Social Networking Sites	.869	20
The Impact of Playing Mobile Games (A)	.732	5
The Impact of Playing Mobile Games (B)	.796	5
Student Learning Activities Questionnaire	.856	15
Total	.855	45

Table 1. Reliability Analysis is performed to analyze the extent to which the developed instruments can produce consistent results. Using SPSS, the results of the reliability analysis is shown in table 1.

The reliability analysis or internal consistency analysis suggests that the developed instruments were acceptable and that the result of the inter-rater reliability analysis indicates homogeneity and consensus ($K = .855$, $N=45$). Specifically, the extent of engagement to social networking sites scale got a reliability coefficient of .869 ($N=20$), the impact of playing mobile games (positive and negative) got a reliability coefficient of .732 ($N=5$) and .796 ($N=5$), respectively. Lastly, the degree of student learning activities questionnaire got a coefficient reliability of .856 ($N=15$). These results suggest that, overall, the developed instruments were acceptable, satisfactory, sufficient, reliable and adequate [19] thus, it can be used for this study.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 The Demographic Profile of the Respondents

3.1.1 Sex

Table 2. Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	342	68.4
Female	158	31.6
Total	500	100.0

Table 2. The frequency distribution of the respondents based on Sex

Table 2 shows the results of the data gathering conducted involving five hundred ($N=500$) first year students taking up

Bachelor of Science in Information Technology in a State University in Central Luzon, Philippines. Results show that 68.4% ($f=342$, $N=500$) are male and 31.6% ($f=158$, $N=500$) are female. It indicates that a computing program like BSIT was still outnumbered by male students than female students. In the global context, countries like the United States of America, Austria, Europe and some countries in the Middle East still faces lack of female students enrolling in computing programs [20]. In the Philippines, the [21] have reported an enormous gap between the number of male and female students enrolled in Information Technology related programs in both Public and Private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) with 97.4% of male students and 2.6% female students. This result was in line with the findings of [22] in a study conducted in a state university with 63% male and 37% female, indicating a huge gap between the numbers of enrollees as to sex. Appianing and Van Eck [23] explain the common factors which affect the enrolment and engagement of female students with Information and Communications Technology (ICT) supported by [24]. Accordingly, factors include stereotyping, the lack of female role models/mentors, the male domain culture of ICT, computer self-efficacy and computer anxiety, family influence, students' relationship with teachers, the impact of computing experience, peer influences, and interest, confidence, and career decisions. These factors affect the women in choosing computing related programs like Information Technology (IT). Findings of this study was in consonance with the reviewed international and local studies denoting the huge difference between the number of male and female enrolled in computing programs such as Information Technology (IT).

3.1.2 Parental Marital Status

Table 3. Parental Marital Status

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Married	371	74.2
Re-married	5	1.0
Never Married	56	11.2
Divorced/Separated	28	5.6
Widowed	27	5.4
Unmarried/Living Together	13	2.6
Total	500	100.0

Table 3. The frequency distribution of the respondents based on Parental Marital Status.

Table 3 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents based on parental marital status. The Federal Student Aid (FAFSA) explains that married status indicate both biological parents undergone marriage and matrimonial ceremony, re-married pertains to a parent married to a stepparent, never married indicates a parent never had a marriage, divorced or separated legally ended-up the relationship, widowed refers to a parent with a partner who has already died, and unmarried/living together refers to parents who did not undergone marriage or matrimonial ceremony [25]. The results of the survey suggests that 74.0% ($f=371$, $N=500$) of the respondents have parents who are married, 1.0% ($f=5$, $N=500$) re-married, 11.2% ($f=56$, $N=500$) never married, 5.6% ($f=28$, $N=500$) divorced or separated, 5.4% ($f=27$, $N=500$) widowed, and 2.6% ($f=13$, $N=500$). Result suggests that students came from a diverse family background, thus an opportunity to collaborate more and exchange relevant and valuable ideas

related to information technology discipline is high.

3.1.3 Monthly Family Income

Table 4. Monthly Family Income

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 9,520	263	52.6
Between 9,921 to 19,040	156	31.2
Between 19,041 to 38,080	56	11.2
Between 38,081 to 66,640	13	2.6
Between 66,641 and above	12	2.4
Total	500	100.0

Table 4. The frequency distribution of the respondents based on Monthly Family Income.

In Table 4, the frequency distribution of the respondents based on the monthly family income shows a greater number of students having a monthly family income of less than 9,520 or 52.6% (f=263, N=500). Meanwhile, there are 31.2% (f=156, N=500) of the respondents having a monthly family income between 9,921 and 19,040, while 11.2% (f=56, N=500) having a monthly family income between 19,041 and 38,080. 2.6% (f=13, N=500) belongs to the 33,081 – 66,640 bracket, and 2.4% (f=12, N=500) in the 66,641 and above bracket. Republic Act 10931 or the [26] can be one of the factors why there are more number of students in the lowest family income bracket who can have access to quality tertiary education in a state university. While Section 2, Article XIV of the [27] focusing on Education, Science and Technology, Arts, Culture, and Sports indicates that the state shall “establish and maintain a system of free public education in the elementary and high school levels”, RA 10931 provides an opportunity for every Filipino to have access to quality tertiary education, thus the results support the increasing ability of families in the lowest income bracket to send their children to school.

3.1.4 Type of Secondary Educational Institution Graduated From

Table 5. Type of Secondary Educational Institution Graduated From

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Public	286	57.2
Private	214	42.8
Total	500	100.0

Table 5. The frequency distribution of the respondents based on the type of secondary educational institution graduated from.

Table 5 presents the result of the survey conducted to the respondents in relation to the type of secondary educational institution graduated from. Results show that 57.2% (f=286, N=500) of the first year students graduated from public schools while 42.8% (f=214, N=500) came from private educational institutions. There is only a 14.4% gap between the type of schools graduated from indicating that the respondents represented both public and private educational institutions in a small gap only. Aside from public schools wherein minimal fees are collected, more senior high school students can complete their secondary education in private secondary schools because of the government means of providing subsidy to students who would like to study in private schools to avoid overcrowding in the public schools through Section 23 of the Implementing Rules and Regulations of Republic Act 10533 [28]. The move of the Philippine

government to support both private and public schools was reflected in the small gap between the students who graduated from public and private schools enrolled in a state university in Central Luzon, Philippines.

3.2 The Extent of Engagement to Social Networking Sites

Table 6. The Extent of Engagement to Social Networking Sites

Items	Very Large Extent		Large Extent		Little Extent		Very Little Extent		Mean
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
	SNS1	116	23.2	357	71.4	23	4.6	4	
SNS2	131	26.2	323	64.6	43	8.6	3	0.6	3.16
SNS3	85	17.0	371	74.2	40	8.0	4	0.8	3.07
SNS4	102	20.4	340	68.0	52	10.4	6	1.2	3.08
SNS5	128	25.6	328	65.6	39	7.8	5	1.0	3.16
SNS6	91	18.2	298	59.6	105	21.0	6	1.2	2.95
SNS7	59	11.8	241	48.2	168	33.6	32	6.4	2.65
SNS8	122	24.4	339	67.8	32	6.4	7	1.4	3.15
SNS9	113	22.6	314	62.8	68	13.6	5	1.0	3.07
SNS10	122	24.4	341	68.2	33	6.6	4	0.8	3.16
SNS11	138	27.6	322	64.4	36	7.2	4	0.8	3.19
SNS12	168	33.6	301	60.2	26	5.2	5	1.0	3.26
SNS13	117	23.4	353	70.6	26	5.2	4	0.8	3.17
SNS14	139	27.8	315	63.0	37	7.4	9	1.8	3.17
SNS15	127	25.4	333	66.6	37	7.4	3	0.6	3.17
SNS16	162	32.4	302	60.4	32	6.4	4	0.8	3.24
SNS17	108	21.6	363	72.6	25	5.0	4	0.8	3.15
SNS18	108	21.6	327	65.4	59	11.8	6	1.2	3.07
SNS19	141	28.2	313	62.6	36	7.2	10	2.0	3.17
SNS20	112	22.4	320	64.0	57	11.4	11	2.2	3.07
Over-all Grand Mean								3.11	
Verbal Description								Large Extent	

Table 6. The result on the evaluation on the extent of engagement to social networking sites by the IT students as presented in the table.

Table 6 shows the results on the evaluation of the respondents on the extent of engagement to social networking sites. Results suggest that the respondent's extent of engagement to social networking sites with regard to its use to make the students sociable, keeping in touch with loved-ones, creating social identity, and getting information about social events was large (SNS1 $\mu=3.17$; SNS2 $\mu=3.16$; SNS7 $\mu=2.95$; SNS7 $\mu=2.65$; SNS8 $\mu=3.15$). Lenhart [29] explains that social media became an important venue for interaction and conversation among teens in America with 76% of the total number of youth using it. Particularly, the following platforms were the most common used as cited by [29]: Facebook (71%), Instagram (52%), Snapchat (41%), Twitter (25%), and Google Plus (25%). In the Philippines, [30] cites that the Philippines was still one of the most active social media and social networking sites users with 76 million active Filipinos in different social media platforms. This data supports the fact that students in the university use social networking sites to become sociable and to connect with different people worldwide. By having an easier means to connect to different parts of the world, results suggest that students' extent of using SNSs to get job related information was large (SNS4 $\mu=3.08$). This implies that the students use SNSs to have essential information which are related to future job or for looking at available jobs applicable

to them. Common social networking websites related for finding a job include Facebook and LinkedIn. Nikolaou [31] explains the use of social networking sites such as LinkedIn and Facebook in searching job and recruiting human resource professionals. However, the study of [31] contradicts the results of this study indicating that more professionals still prefer job boards than job postings in different social networking sites. One of the reasons may be attributed to the difference in generation of the respondents involved in this study, and in the study of [31]. Entertainment is one of the reasons why people use social media and different social networking sites. On the extent of using SNSs for the purpose of entertainment, respondents viewed it on a large extent (SNS11 $\mu = 3.19$, SNS15 $\mu = 3.17$, SNS11 $\mu = 3.24$, SNS10 $\mu = 3.16$, SNS11 $\mu = 3.17$, SNS11 $\mu = 3.07$). Results show that respondents use SNSs to share fun and entertaining pictures, as a relief from academic stress, for watching movies, reading news and articles, and discovering and developing new set of skills. Leggatt [32] cites that more people have been using the internet and social media including SNSs for entertainment purposes. United States, Europe and China have been cited for their shift from using the conventional platform for entertainment to digital media. In the Philippines, according to the We Are Social's [33], 71% of the entire population are active social media users. These results can be associated with the extent of engagement of Filipinos to social media and to the result found in this study in relation to the engagement of the students to SNSs for entertainment purposes. SNSs used for academic purposes were evaluated as part of this study. Results show that the respondents viewed the extent of engagement to SNSs for academic purposes were large indicating the following mean scores: SNS3 $\mu = 3.07$, SNS5 $\mu = 3.16$, SNS9 $\mu = 3.07$, SNS12 $\mu = 3.26$, SNS13 $\mu = 3.17$, SNS14 $\mu = 3.17$, SNS17 $\mu = 3.15$ and SNS18 $\mu = 3.07$. Engagement to SNSs has large extent in terms of using it to seek help from the teachers, sharing new ideas, online academic group discussions, research works, and learning about curricular requirements, communicating in line with preparation for examinations, collaborative learning, and solving academic problems. Segaren [34] explains the important role of social media in higher education. Accordingly, professors and college instructors can use social media and different SNSs to enhance and further improve the quality of teaching and learning. These platforms also increased the engagement of the students because it was a less formal way for professors and instructors to communicate, thus showing a more personal side while improving the teacher-student relationship. In consonance with the results of this study in relation to the engagement of IT students to SNS focusing on the academic components, [34] and [35] explain the positive impact and the advantages of incorporating social media and SNSs in the teaching and learning activities. It was noted that these tools provide opportunities to students to improve their prior knowledge, or grasp new insights about a certain topic. Gemma and Angel [36] affirms that SNSs and other forms of social media were utilized by scholars to disseminate research results and follow other scholars to get in touch with and be updated to recent trends and developments in their respective fields. This makes SNSs valuable to people in the academic industry.

3.3 The Impact of Playing Mobile Games

Table 7. The Positive Impact of Playing Mobile Games

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Mean
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
	MG1	116	23.2	357	71.4	23	4.6	4	
MG2	131	26.2	323	64.6	43	8.6	3	0.6	3.20
MG3	85	17.0	371	74.2	40	8.0	4	0.8	3.08
MG4	102	20.4	340	68.0	52	10.4	6	1.2	2.77
MG5	128	25.6	328	65.6	39	7.8	5	1.0	2.95
Over-all Mean (Positive)								2.94	
Verbal Description								Agree	

Table 7. Tables 7 presents the result of the evaluation made by the IT students on the positive impacts of playing mobile games.

Table 8. The Negative Impact of Playing Mobile Games

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Mean
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
	MG6	91	18.2	298	59.6	105	21.0	6	
MG7	59	11.8	241	48.2	168	33.6	32	6.4	2.07
MG8	122	24.4	339	67.8	32	6.4	7	1.4	2.17
MG9	113	22.6	314	62.8	68	13.6	5	1.0	2.02
MG10	122	24.4	341	68.2	33	6.6	4	0.8	2.18
Over-all Mean (Negative)								2.10	
Verbal Description								Disagree	

Table 8. The result on the evaluation made by the IT student on the negative impacts of playing mobile games is presented in Table 8.

Today's generation of learners is more exposed to different technologies and advancements. This can lead to positive and negative impacts. In Table 7 and Table 8, the positive and negative impacts of playing mobile games were evaluated to see how the IT students viewed mobile games in either positive or negative way. Based from the results of this study, it was found out that generally, playing mobile games has moderate impact in the lives of the IT students (overall $\mu = 2.52$). This means that the students were engaged and fond of playing mobile games but still possesses some extent of reservations and limitations. Specifically, students thought that playing mobile games can help them improve their physical activities (MG1 $\mu = 2.68$) since there were mobile games which require the end-users or players to be engaged into physical activities such as Pokemon Go!, Zombies, Run!, Geocaching, SpecTrek, Ballstrike, The Walk, Superhero Workout, and Jump, Jump Froggy [37]. Mobile games relating to puzzle games and role playing games (RPG) were perceived to have moderate impact (MG2 $\mu = 3.20$) among the IT students because they thought that such can help them enhance and developed their critical, logical, and analytical thinking skills. Fernandez, Palaoag, and Dela Cruz [38] can be of support in the findings of this study since the authors claim that mobile games utilization has an average effect on the development of students' problem solving skills, critical thinking and logical thinking. On the other hand, mobile games designed as additional learning materials which helps students to learn new things (MG3 $\mu = 3.08$), mobile games that were designed to inspire the students to live a healthy lifestyle to improve their well-being (MG4 $\mu = 2.77$) and mobile games designed to contribute to the development of the community (MG3 $\mu = 2.95$) were viewed to have moderate impact to IT students. Overall, the positive effects of playing mobile games have moderate impact among the IT students, denoting that

the use of mobile games by the students can be of help in improving their holistic development. Meanwhile, the negative impacts of playing mobile games generally got a minor impact rating among IT students. It means that IT students disagree on the stated negative impacts and that they try not to reap the negative effects of playing mobile games. Specifically, most of the IT students disagree that playing mobile games distract them in performing more important tasks (MG6 $\mu = 2.07$), affects how they interact with other people socially (MG3 $\mu = 2.07$), makes them spend more financial resources (MG3 $\mu = 2.17$), causes to have sleeping problems (MG3 $\mu = 2.17$), and loss of productivity and effectiveness in performing tasks (MG3 $\mu = 2.18$). Results suggests that the IT students know their limitations and that they only engaged in playing mobile games mostly for its positive effects. Another insight that can be drawn is that IT students were well informed of the negative effects, thus making them aware of it lessens the negative impacts among themselves.

3.4 The Degree of Learning Experiences

Table 9. The Degree of Learning Experiences

Items	Strongly Agree		Agree		Disagree		Strongly Disagree		Mean
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
LE1	96	19.2	314	62.8	75	15.0	15	3.0	2.98
LE2	134	26.8	350	70.0	13	2.6	3	0.6	3.23
LE3	83	16.6	357	71.4	56	11.2	4	0.8	3.04
LE4	76	15.2	338	67.6	75	15.0	11	2.2	2.96
LE5	66	13.2	344	68.8	80	16.0	10	2.0	2.93
LE6	67	13.4	287	57.4	128	25.6	18	3.6	2.81
LE7	66	13.2	277	55.4	143	28.6	14	2.8	2.79
LE8	113	22.6	344	68.8	40	8.0	3	0.6	3.13
LE9	80	16.0	345	69.0	67	13.4	8	1.6	2.99
LE10	72	14.4	358	71.6	63	12.6	7	1.4	2.99
LE11	96	19.2	364	72.8	37	7.4	3	0.6	3.11
LE12	79	15.8	350	70.0	57	11.4	14	2.8	2.99
LE13	117	23.4	333	66.6	45	9.0	5	1.0	3.12
LE14	82	16.4	295	59.0	107	21.4	16	3.2	2.87
LE15	92	18.4	360	72.0	43	8.6	5	1.0	3.08
Over-all Grand Mean							3.00		
Verbal Description							Agree		

Table 9. The evaluation on the degree of learning experiences among IT students is presented in table 9.

In general, the IT students' evaluation on the degree of learning experiences got an overall grand mean of 3.00 (Verbal Description = Agree). This means that the student frequently practice the learning activities stated in the questionnaire. More specifically, the IT students frequently use the library and learning resource centers to learn new information, conduct research and enrich their knowledge ($\mu=2.98$, SA = 19.2%, A = 62.8%, D = 15.0%, SD = 3.0%). Trombetta [39] and Cooke [40] explains and cites the importance of libraries and learning resource centers in the university. Accordingly, libraries are essential because they offer free educational resources to everyone resulting to higher opportunities to learn new things, improved reading and comprehension skills, higher academic achievement, and positive attitudes towards learning. Learning resource centers meanwhile provide a centralized source of supplemental resources and materials essential for college education. The use of computer and information technology tools to equip the students with the necessary skills related to their respective

programs ($\mu=3.23$, SA = 26.8%, A = 70.0%, D = 2.6%, SD = 0.6%), the engagement to course learning experiences such as term papers, researches, and culminating activities ($\mu=3.04$, SA = 16.6%, A = 71.4%, D = 11.2%, SD = 0.8%), participating in writing experiences such as technical report writing and creative writings ($\mu=2.96$, SA = 15.2%, A = 67.6%, D = 15.0%, SD = 2.2%), engaging to scientific and quantitative experiences such as experiments and programming ($\mu=2.93$, SA = 13.2%, A = 68.8%, D = 16.0%, SD = 2.0%), attending to arts, music, and theater activities and events ($\mu=2.81$, SA = 13.4%, A = 57.4%, D = 25.6%, SD = 3.6%), participating in different clubs and organizations ($\mu=2.80$, SA = 13.2%, A = 55.4%, D = 28.6%, SD = 2.8%), expressing the students thoughts and ideas through meaningful conversation with friends and classmates ($\mu=3.13$, SA = 22.6%, A = 68.8%, D = 8.0%, SD = 0.6%), engaging to personal development activities such as spiritual development, and gender and development activities ($\mu=2.99$, SA = 16.0%, A = 69.0%, D = 13.4%, SD = 1.6%), engaging to variety of conversation topics ($\mu=2.99$, SA = 14.4%, A = 71.6%, D = 12.6%, SD = 1.4%), using of the things the students learned in the classroom in different venues of learning ($\mu=3.11$, SA = 19.2%, A = 72.8%, D = 7.4%, SD = 0.6%), attending flag raising ceremonies and other activities relevant to fostering nationalism ($\mu=2.99$, SA = 15.8%, A = 70.0%, D = 11.4%, SD = 2.8%), socializing with friends and developing social skills through the use of student centers and lounges ($\mu=3.12$, SA = 23.4%, A = 66.6%, D = 9.0%, SD = 1.0%), engaging to sports activities in the university ($\mu=2.89$, SA = 16.4%, A = 59.0%, D = 21.4%, SD = 3.2%) and engaging to meaningful conversation with instructors and professors ($\mu=3.08$, SA = 18.4%, A = 72.0%, D = 8.6%, SD = 1.0%) were all evaluated as frequently experienced and observed by the IT students. All of the items got a high rating indicating that the IT students in the college were active in participating and engaging themselves in the different areas of learning experiences in the university. Johnson [41] explains that learning experiences such as the learning experiences included in this study were essential for students to acquire as new set of skills and knowledge that may lead to better opportunities. GettingSmart.com [42] asserts the importance of learning experience design in the higher education indicating that a learning experience can create relevant, engaging, and memorable educational experiences among the students. Kakaris [43] supports the literatures cited and explains that learning experiences must be in consonance with the requirements essential for the completion of courses. That is, the learning activities resulting to learning experiences must be in agreement and in complementary with the course offering to achieve an optimal results and favorable outcomes. In the university, results shows that the learning experiences of the students were in complementary with the programs and course offerings of the university, making them more relevant and effective.

4 CONCLUSION

This study was conducted to evaluate the extent of engagement of the IT students in social networking, the impact of playing mobile games, and the degree of learning experiences to serve as a basis for developing program interventions and activities in the college. In general, this study found out that in terms of sex, the number of male students was larger than female student by 36.8%, 74.2% have parental marital status who were married, more than half

(52.6%) of the students belongs in the lowest income bracket with income less than 9,520, and a small gap between the type of secondary educational institutions graduated from with 57.2% from public and 42.8% from private. The results of the evaluation made on the extent of engagement to social media shows a large extent based from the overall computed grand mean of 3.11. In terms of the results on the impact of playing mobile games, results show that the respondents viewed mobile games having a moderate positive impact and minor negative impact as reflected from the overall computed grand mean for positive and negative impacts ($\mu=2.94$, $\mu=2.10$). Lastly, the degree of learning experiences of the IT students show that students frequently participated, engaged, attended and involved themselves into the different learning activities and experiences in the university resulting to an overall computed grand mean of 3.00. The evaluation made may be the basis for developing intervention programs and activities.

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